

Voicing the Marginalization of the Fair Sex: An analysis of Anita Rau Badami's Tamarind Mem and Shauna Singh Baldwin's The Selector of Souls

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In spite of the advancement in science and technology, and living standard of people, the evils of gender discrimination can be easily noticed at any corner of the world whether it may be a developed or a developing country. Men hold the reins of all the main activities of the social, political or economic arenas. Love for a male child in India is to such an extent that from the times immemorial we are killing our little girls during childbirth or before conception. This disparaging act not only breaches the doctrine of equality between male and female but also can throw Indian society in such a stage where there will be no woman and the Bollywood movie *Matrubhumi* or *A Nation Without Women* exemplify it well. Shauna Singh Baldwin has dealt with this sex selection issue in her novel *The Selector of Souls*.

She says, "There is no question, this is a terrible problem, and it's a very silent problem" (theglobeandmail.com). The novel unfolds the widening epidemic of daughter aversion that is distorting the Indian society leading it towards a nation without women. The story of the novel centres around two leading female characters of two different classes; Damini, a Hindu widow who is a destitute and Anupam or Sister Anu, who is married to Vikas, businessman of Delhi. Set in a village named Gurkot in Himalayan region, a young woman Leela gives birth to her third child, actually a baby daughter, with the help of her mother, Damini. But the birth of the daughter brings no joy to the family instead the mother is humiliated for giving birth to a female child as most of the Indian woman is abused and cursed by the family and society for delivering a Baby girl. And the father, Chunnilal, a truck driver, refuses to name the child and says, "She isn't worth naming" anticipating the cost of dowry. Realising the poignant, non-extant position of the female sex in the deeply ingrained "classic patriarchal belt", in which a girl suffers from the crisis of "Someone", Damini shockingly enacts the plan to Sacrifice

her granddaughter in the name of Anamika Devi and Lord Golunath proclaiming that this world is not fit for girls and women and appeals, “Release this Atman, girl body. Let it return to the place that continues long before and long after this word. Let it take shape when this world is better for girls” (09)

On the other hand, the subplot of the novel narrates the tale of Sister Anu (Anupam) who wants to remain unmarried and childless to stop the enormous rate of population growth of the country. However, like every Indian girl, she is conditioned to believe that marriage is a vocation, and a girl has no existence outside the periphery of the threshold that forces her to get married no matter even if she is reluctant. But the marriage proves to be a nightmare for Anu, her domain being strictly defined and confined with a complete acceptance of husband’s decisions. Like most of the women of the traditional family, she is brutally beaten and even raped by her husband, Vikas, and marital rape is a fact which still is not accounted to accept in Indian families. Ameer Sultan, in her article “Battered in the Safe Haven: Women and Domestic Violence” well articulates:

Neither social scientists nor historians have labelled violence in the family as a social problem. It remains invisible, because whatever is happening within the four walls of the house is regarded as a ‘private issue’. Any interference in this matter is believed as a breach of ‘privacy of a person’. (37)

When Anu gives birth to a daughter enforce out of rape by her husband, the delivery of the baby is declared as a disgrace on the family and the mother is humiliated and disrespected because Vikas wanted “a boy”, a boy, a boy, everyone wants a son” (47) To avoid the disgrace of the family he sends his daughter Chetna to Rano in Canada despite the truth that Anu was reluctant to send her away, when Anu tells her uncle Sharad that her mother in law wishes her to leave the house because “She wants Vikas to have a wife who can produce a son” (95) but, irony is that even her uncle supports the demand of bridegroom’s family and suggests Anu have a “boy” with the help of Ultrasound techniques.

Damini herself had been the sufferer of gender discrimination because She was born as the fifth daughter of her mother who was humiliated because the father “had found a second bride to bear him sons” and her mother sets herself to burn alive. She bewails:

I killed my mother by taking shape, entering the world when I did. Couldn’t have I waited ? Why didn’t I listen to her wishes and die in her womb? Couldn’t have I gone to some other woman and not added to the burdens of a woman who already had four daughters? (230)

In this way, Shauna Singh Baldwin, in spite of being an outsider, shows close observation and understanding of the sensitive problem of Indian society, i.e. the issue of sex selection and marginalization of the second sex, writing outspokenly against the traditional customs and the society that produced her.

Furthermore, the present paper aims to discuss Anita Rau Badami’s novel *Tamarind Mem* in which the novelist accuses the conventional rules of the society which oppress women. In *Tamarind Mem*, Saroja, who desires to be doctor, is forced to get married by her parents. Badami highlights the necessity of a marriage for a woman in the words of Saroja’s mother, “a woman without a husband is like sand without the river. No man to protect you and every evil wind will blow over your body” (158).

Saroja feels caught in her traditional role as an Indian wife and mother who must always be the epitome of an ideal woman-cooking, keeping the house and raising children. Saroja finds no way out of the disappointments trap but through a whiplash of words. Most of the time, she is quietly contented as a railway wife, responsible mother, trying to line up to the band epithets sowed in her mind by her mother. She struggles to keep her faith in these beliefs. Saroja’s in-between life was an exact fact in every women’s married life. Saroja proves women’s regular character of leading

their life like a candle to give light to their next generation. She sends everyone away from her life like a tamarind tree and takes to the railroad, a middle class, modern-day sanyasi, seeing the place that her husband would not take her to on his frequent and routined business trips. Saroja, a Tamarind Mem never allows anyone, Under her to live. Her love for her family members is only a distance love. Badami portrays Saroja as a frustrated woman trapped in the cultural expectations of the period. Only after her husband's death and her daughter's maturity may make Saroja leave her traditional role and travel as she pleases.

Both the novels stand as a testimony to the marginalization and subjugation of women in a male-dominated society. The women of today need to reach a new stage towards greater independence of choice and self as Swami Vivekanand has remarked there is no chance for the welfare of the world unless the condition of the woman is improved. It is not possible for a bird to fly on only one wing. There is no hope for that family or country where there is no estimation of women, where they live in sadness. For this reason, they have to be uplifted and empowered.

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